

Murad Mir-Zada

Halic University, Istanbul

MA Candidate in Architecture, BArch RIBA Part 1

muradmirzadeh@yahoo.com**UDC 72.03****PRESERVATION PROPOSAL OF BODRUM MESİH PASHA
MOSQUE (MYRELAION MONASTERY) IN ISTANBUL**

Abstract: After the conquest of Istanbul in 1453, most Byzantine structures were converted into mosques within the scope of the Deconstruction policy, but there are also church structures still actively used by Orthodox and Catholic communities. In this study, where the establishment processes of these historical structures serving two different civilizations and two different religions are examined, the social aspect of monastic life along with the architectural space layouts and historical interactions have been determined.

Since the units belonging to the monastic organizations located within the boundaries of Istanbul disappeared over time and only the church structures have survived to the present the study examined the history and architectural features of Bodrum Mesih Pasha Mosque (Myrelaion Monastery), an analysis of the old restoration works, as well as its current state.

Key words: Byzantine structures, monastery, restoration, Istanbul, architecture history.

Introduction: Among the Byzantine monasteries, one of the monasteries that attracts attention with its different architecture is the Byzantine Emperor Romanus I. Dec. It is the Myrelaion monastery founded by Lecapenus and currently serving as the Bodrum Messih Pasha Mosque.

The Myrelaion Monastery was first mentioned by Pierre Gilles of Albi. Gilles, Emperor of the French, I. He stayed in Istanbul from 1544 to October 1547, when he was sent by Francis for a scientific purpose and, in addition to his other work, collected systematic notes on the ancient ruins in the city. Although the exact boundaries of the ninth district of the city are still unknown today and are the subject of debate, it is known that it covers Laleli region and part of Aksaray (Striker, 1981). In accordance with Gilles' description, the Bodrum Mosque is also located right in the middle of the area known as the ninth district. The area where the Myrelaion Monastery is located is referred to in Byzantine sources as Blancha or Blanga, the place where the Lycus river flows into the Marmara Sea (Figure 1. (Striker, 1981).

The infrastructure of the Bodrum Messianic Pasha Mosque was first examined by Wulzinger in 1913. Wulzinger, after detailed examinations, said

that the infrastructure, about which there are many opposing ideas, is part of Romanus' funeral church, and dates to the 10th century. he specified it as the first quarter of the century (Wulzinger, 1913). Wulzinger has never doubted that the infrastructure and the church are a homogeneous structure and that they were designed together and built on the same date (Wulzinger, 1913). However, some researchers have argued in the opposite direction since the masonry technique of the church and infrastructure is different (Striker, 1981).

The Myrelaion Monastery and the church connected to it were built by Romanus as a funeral place for his family, and 6 people from the Decapeni family were buried here between 922-961 (Striker, 1981). First, Theodora, the wife of Romanus, was buried in Myrelaion Monastery in 922. Theodora was followed by her eldest son Christopher, who died in 931. in 946, his other son Constantine was buried in the same grave as his wife Helena, who died a little past the year 940. Finally, the body of Romanus, who died as a monk in exile in 948, was brought to the Myrelaion Monastery from the island of Prote to be buried next to his wife (Striker, 1981). Romanus, of course, is not the last Lecapeni to be buried in the monastery. in 961, the emperor 7. During the excavations carried out by Naumann, the graves were removed from the infrastructure and moved to another location.

Information about the founding date and bani of the Bodrum Mosque is given in the book *Hadikat-ul Cevami*, the oldest systematic history of Istanbul Mosques, written by Hafiz Hüseyin Ayvansarayi in 1781 and published in 1864. Considering that there are no other archival materials, the book can be expressed as the oldest Turkish source about structure. The monastery church, which continued its function until the conquest of the city, was converted into a mosque by the grand vizier of the period, Mesih Ali Pasha, in 1501 (Ayvansarayi, 1781). In other words, the structure was built half a century after the conquest by Sultan II. It was converted into a mosque during the Bayezid period (1481-1512). Although Bodrum is called Messih Pasha Mosque in dedication to his banis, the name of Bodrum was given to the structure by the people because of its infrastructure. Although there are not many documents related to the period when the building was used as a mosque in the Ottoman archives, it is seen that it served continuously until the fire of 1911, except for the repair times. After the fire of 1911, the structure, which remained dormant for a while, was repaired, and continued to serve as a mosque again. (Striker, 1981). As part of the Ottoman celebration policy, an altar, a wooden pulpit, and a cut stone minaret were added to the structure, which was converted into a mosque in 1501.

The most comprehensive research on the architecture of Myrelaion was based on a study conducted by Striker in 1981. The main source where the building stages are systematically recorded on drawings was published by

Striker in 1981. In 1965, excavations related to the investigation of infrastructure were carried out by Rudolf Naumann thanks to drilling works on the eastern front. The cistern excavations were completed with drilling works in the direction of the north and east sides (Naumann, 1965).

**Figure 1. Myrelaion Monastery
(Paspates, 1877)**

**Figure 2. Sectional
Perspective (Striker, 1981)**

The current condition, damages, original condition, and improvement methods of the Bodrum Mesih Pasha Mosque, which has a different layout from all Byzantine monasteries located within and outside the borders of Turkey, were examined. No other monastic structure with a space layout similar to the monastery, consisting of a palace, rotunda, and church complex, has been identified. Although it contains features that can be detected in different structures, such as being built by an emperor and designed as a tomb structure, the monk is an example in terms of collecting wards, trapezes, and other monastery units in a single palace structure. The study, in which the damage and period analyses are carried out, the current condition is documented, and the intervention recommendations are interpreted, is intended to be a guide for more in-depth research.

Methodology: It is aimed to study the monastery structures located within the boundaries of Istanbul, where all units except the main structures have succumbed to time and disappeared, to identify and document the monastery architecture. Structures located in different cities and countries have been investigated within the scope of the study to determine the spatial patterns of monastic structures, which are mostly accessible to churches to this day. After examining the structures located outside Istanbul and the structures in Istanbul, an evaluation was made comparing the similar and different features of the Bodrum Mesih Pasha Mosque.

The aim is to be able to develop intervention methods for the protection and transmission of the Bodrum Mesih Pasha Mosque, which is an example in terms of architectural space layout, to future generations.

Result: After the studies aimed at determining the structures established within the city limits, monastic institutions established in other cities of the country outside the borders of Istanbul and in many countries, especially Greece, were examined in the layout, plan, and facade system. In the light of all the data and visual sources that have been identified, research studies have been carried out to determine and date the current condition and original state of Myrelaion Monastery, an important Byzantine monastery.

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Murad Mir-Zadə

İstanbulda Bodrum Məsih Paşa Məscidinin (Mirelayon Manastırının) qorunması təklifi

Açar sözlər: Bizans tikililəri, monastır, bərpa, İstanbul, memarlıq tarix.

Bizans binalarının əksəriyyəti 1453-cü ildə İstanbulun fəthindən sonra dekomunizasiya siyasətinə uyğun olaraq məscidlərə çevrilsə də, bunların arasında hələ də pravoslav və katolik icmaları tərəfindən fəal şəkildə istifadə olunan kilsə binaları var. İki fərqli sivilizasiyaya və iki fərqli dinə xidmət edən bu tarixi tikililərin təməl proseslərini araşdıran bu tədqiqat, memarlıq və tarixi qarşılıqlı əlaqələr ilə yanaşı, monastır həyatının sosial tərəfini də müəyyənləşdirir.

Təəssüf ki, İstanbul sərhədləri daxilində yerləşən monastır strukturlarının növləri zamanla yoxa çıxmış və yalnız kilsə binaları günümüzə gəlib çatmışdır. Tədqiqat çərçivəsində Bodrum Məsih Paşa Məscidi'nin (Mirelayon Manastırı) tarixi, memarlıq xüsusiyyətləri, bugünə qədər aparılmış bərpa işlərinin analizi və eyni zamanda hazırki vəziyyəti araşdırılmışdır.

Мурад Мир-заде

**Предложение по сохранению мечети Мессия-паши Бодрум
(Монастырь Мирелайон) в Стамбуле**

Ключевые слова: византийские сооружения, монастырь, реставрация, Стамбул, история архитектуры.

Хотя большинство византийских построек были преобразованы в мечети в соответствии с политикой декоммунизации после завоевания Стамбула в 1453 году, среди них есть церковные постройки, которые до сих пор активно используются православными и католическими общинами. В этом исследовании, в котором изучаются процессы основания этих исторических построек, служащих двум разным цивилизациям и двум разным религиям, наряду с их архитектурной планировкой и историческим взаимодействием, также определяется социальный аспект монашеской жизни.

Из-за того, что подразделения монастырских организаций, расположенных в границах Стамбула, со временем исчезли, и сохранились только церковные постройки. В рамках исследования были изучены история, архитектурные особенности мечети Бодрум Мессия-паша (Монастырь Мирелайон), анализ старых реставрационных работ, проведенных на сегодняшний день, а также ее нынешнее состояние.